

**HUMAN ENVIRONMENT AND INTERNATIONAL ECONOMIC LAW:
EXPLORING THE IMPORTANCE OF STOCKHOLM DECLARATION OF 1972**

Kolawole Kazeem, OYEYEMI*

ABSTRACT.

In July, 1972, the UN conference on the human environment was held in Stockholm Sweden. The conference was adjudged in many respects, the most successful international conference held at the time. In a two-week period, the conference adopted not only the basic declaration but also a detailed resolution on institutional and financial arrangement. No doubt, the Stockholm declaration is of practical importance in international relations more particularly on the activities of humankind in relation to his environment. It introduced among others two fundamental principles; sustainable development and intergenerational equity. Its principle 2, 3, 5 and 21 brought about the idea of conserving natural resources onto the agenda of international Economic law, until this point international economic law had sought to define and strengthen the rights of sovereign states to exploit their natural resources. Today, international financial institutions tailored their financial relations with developing nations along these pivotal principles of the Stockholm declarations. This paper explores the importance of the Stockholm declaration to international economic law.

INTRODUCTION

The Stockholm conference of 1972¹ basically is one on human environment.² The explicit acknowledgement that humanity and nature are in symbiotic relationship³ i.e. both depend upon each other emphasis both the necessity of a good environment for the survival of humankind and humankind responsibility in protecting the environment.⁴ However, the Stockholm Declaration is not simply concerned with environmental issues in strictest sense. Development and socio- economic issues are also of importance.⁵

The Stockholm Conference marked the beginning of the third and modern era of international environmental law⁶. The Stockholm meeting produced a number of significant outcomes including the establishment of UNEP (United Nation Environmental Programme) and the adoption of the Stockholm Declaration⁷ setting out twenty-six Principles and an Action Plan containing 109 recommendations.⁸ Philippe Sands observed thus:

“The Stockholm Conference set the scene for international activities at the regional and global level, and influenced legal and institutional developments up to and beyond UNCED. Developments in this period are of two types: those directly related to Stockholm and follow-up actions; and those indirectly

*Kolawole Kazeem, OYEMYMI, Lecturer, Department of Public law, Faculty of law, University of Miaduguri, Borno State, Nigeria.

¹ It was adjudged as the most successful at the time. See Louis B. Sohn, The Stockholm Declaration on Human environment, Harvard International Law Journal, 413, Volume 14, Number 3, Summer 1973, Pg 423. See also John Baylis, Steve Smith. 2005. The Globalization of World Politics (3rd ed). Oxford. Oxford University Press. P.454-455

² See Stockholm Declaration on the Human Environment, in report of the United Nations Conference on the Human Environment, UN Doc. A/CONF.48/ 14, at 2 and Coord. 1 (1972).

³ For a list and the detailed content of the 109 recommendations, see United Nations Environment Programme, Recommendations for Action at the International Level, <http://www.unep.org/Documents.multilingual/Default.asp?DocumentD=97&ArticleID=1506&l=en> (last visited Mar. 17, 2013)

⁴See Duncan French, Conventions, Treaties and other response to Global Issues, International Guidelines and Principles, Vol. I, Pg 8.

⁵ Ibid at pg 8 – 9.

⁶ See Louis B. Sohn, The Stockholm Declaration on Human environment. Op. Cit at FN 1. p. 423.

⁷ Declaration of the UN Conference on the Human Environment, Stockholm, 5–16 June 1972, contained in Report of the UN Conference on the Human Environment, UN Doc. A/CONF.48/14.

⁸ Ibid and Corr.1 (1972).

related thereto. The period was marked by: a proliferation of international environmental organisations (including those established by treaty) and greater efforts by existing institutions to address environmental issues; the development of new sources of international environmental obligations from acts of such organisations; new environmental norms established by treaty; the development of new techniques for implementing environmental standards; including environmental impact assessment and access to information; and the formal integration of environment and development, particularly in relation to international trade and development assistance.”⁹

This paper explores the importance of the Stockholm Declaration of 1972 to international economic law with particular reference to two of its fundamental principles: the principle of sustainable development and intergenerational equity that have strong bearing and relation to trends in international economic law.

REASONS FOR CONVENING THE STOCKHOLM CONFERENCE OF 1972

The complex relationship between humankind and the environment has attracted attention for centuries.¹⁰ International rules for the management and protection of natural resources, however, emerged in the past century. After the creations of the U.N. (United Nation) and notwithstanding the lack of a specific environmental mandate in the U.N. Charter,¹¹ the U.N.

⁹ See Philippe Sands, *Principles of International Environmental Law* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2003), pg 40.

¹⁰ See Roland Bechmann, *Trees and Man: The Forest in the Middle Ages* (1990); J.Donald Hughes, *Pan's travail: Environmental Problems of the Ancient Greeks and Romans* (1993); Ronald J. Rychlak, *People as Part of Nature: Reviewing the Law of the Mother*, 13 STAN. ENVTL. L.J. 451, 456 (1994) (reviewing *Law of the Mother: Protecting Indigenous People in Protected Areas* (Elizabeth Kemp ed., 1993)).

¹¹ The environment is not mentioned in the U.N. Charter, nor is it mentioned in the agreements setting up the international institutions that were created after the Second World War to promote a new international

and its specialized agencies began in earnest to deal with environmental concerns in the context of economic and social issues.¹² The first international treaties adopted after the creation of the U.N. regulated specific environmental problems, media, and species.¹³ Despite these initiatives, however, there was neither a coherent strategy nor a comprehensive set of international norms on the environment. In addition, no international institution was established to promote and coordinate global efforts on the environment. In the early 1960s,¹⁴ environmentalism emerged on the national scene, prompted by the release of scientific evidence on the Planet's decline.¹⁵ Realizing that national measures to deal with environmental degradation would not be sufficient to reverse the Earth's decline, environmentalists called on their governments and on the international community to take steps to formulate a coherent and comprehensive international environmental strategy.¹⁶

The U.N. answered these calls by convening an international conference on the human environment, the Stockholm Conference in 1975,¹⁷ which became the first U.N. gathering to put the environment center-stage on the global agenda.¹⁸ The General Assembly agreed to ECOSOC's (Economic and social committee) request and decided that the proposed Conference would provide a framework for comprehensive consideration within the U.N. of the problems of the human environment in order to focus the attention of Governments and

architecture, the International Bank for Reconstruction and Development ("IBRD") and the International Monetary Fund ("IMF").

¹² See DeSombre, Elizabeth (2006). *Global Environmental Institutions*. Rutledge. pp. 22-23.

¹³ See, e.g., Convention on Third Party Liability in the Field of Nuclear Energy, July 29, 1960, 956 U.N.T.S. 251; Antarctic Treaty, Dec. 1, 1959, 12 U.S.T. 794, 1961 U.N.T.S. 72; International Convention for the Protection of Birds, Oct. 8, 1950, 1968 U.N.T.S. 187; International Convention for the Regulation of Whaling, Dec. 2, 1946, 62 Stat. 1716, 1953 U.N.T.S. 74.

¹⁴ Rachel Carson published her famous book, *Silent Spring*, in 1962. The book was one of the most influential and is credited by many for having created the modern environmental movement. See Rachel Carson, *Silent Spring* (2002).

¹⁵ See, e.g., Roderick F. Nash, *American Environmentalism: Readings in Conservation* (1989); Ramachandra Guha, *Environmentalism: A Global History* (1999)

¹⁶ See Wayland Kennet, *The Stockholm Conference on the Human Environment*, 48 INT'L AFF. 33(1972).

¹⁷ On the Stockholm Conference, see *supra* note 2 and accompanying text. See also Kennet, *supra* note 38, at 34; Louis B. Sohn, *The Stockholm Declaration on the Human Environment*, 14 *Harvard International Law Journal*. 423 (1973).

¹⁸ See E. Thomas Sullivan, *The Stockholm Conference: A Step Toward Global Environmental Cooperation and Involvement*, 6 *IND. L. REv.* 267 (1972-1973).

public opinion on the importance and urgency of this question and also to identify those aspects of it that can only or best be solved through international co-operation and agreement.¹⁹ Delegates from 113 States (nearly all the members of the international community at the time)²⁰ attended the United Nations Conference on the Human Environment. The delegates deliberated on the state of the environment and the need to take urgent action(s) to prevent its further degradation.²¹

STOCKLHOM DECLARATION- MAIN ISSUES

The Stockholm declaration of 1972, as already noted established the basic rule of international environmental law. In general, it has the following structure. It starts with a general invocation which links the environment with fundamental human rights; it deals with the management of natural resource and threat to pollution.²² The relationship between the environment and development viewed as the main area of confrontation since 1972, between the industrialized and developing countries was next considered²³. Related to the problem of development is the section on planning and environmental policies with the inclusion of demographic policies.²⁴ Principle 21 of Stockholm Declaration, according to many writers and international court of justice entered the body of international customary law.²⁵ This principle recognizes States' sovereignty over their natural resources, coupled with their responsibility not to cause environmental damage.²⁶ Further, the declaration supports

¹⁹ See ECOSOC Res. 1346 (XVL), UN Doc. E/Res/1346/XVL (July 30, 1968).

²⁰ See Report of the U.N. Conference on the Human Environment, op. Cit. n 2.

²¹ Ibid at 33- 34.

²² Duncan French, op.cit at n 4 at pg. 4-5

²³ Ibid at pg 5.

²⁴ See Report of the U.N. Conference On the Human Environment, Op. cit. n 2, Principle.16.

²⁵ See also Philippe Sands, Principles of International Environmental Law Ch. 2 (2d ed. 2003); at 38 (calling Stockholm Declaration Principles 21-24 most relevant principles of Stockholm Declaration from legal perspective).

²⁶ Report of the U.N. Conference on the Human Environment, Op.cit. at n 2, Principle 21.

international cooperation's. A principle 26 which warns against weapons of mass destructions concludes the Stockholm declaration.

At this juncture, need to say, that Principle 8 to 14 are of special importance to the crux of this paper, its provisions covers the realm of environment and development. Principle 8 set the tone for the general background for development. For clarity purpose, its provision state inter alia:

Principle 8

“Economic and social development is essential for ensuring a favourable living and working environment for man and for creating conditions on earth that are necessary for the improvement of the quality of life.”

Principle 9 and 11 are of greater importance for the future. While principle 9 expressly stipulated that environmental deficiencies generated by the condition of underdevelopment and natural disaster pose grave problems and can be best remedied by accelerated development through finance and technological assistance as a supplement to the domestic effort of developing countries. Principle 11 stressed a very important aspect of the link between the environment and development, namely it postulates that the environment policies of state should enhanced not only the present and future development potential of developing countries, and that they should not hamper the attainment of better living conditions for all, and that step should be taking by states and international organizations with a view to

reaching an agreement on meeting the possible national and international economic consequences resulting from the applications of economic measures.²⁷

It is submitted that all the principles encapsulated in the Stockholm declaration emphasised the necessity for economic development in relation to developing countries and hinted at the inevitability of the conflicts between development and the protection of the environment.

Therefore, the approach adopted at Stockholm declaration of 1972 heralded a modern view at the position of the developing state, such that stress on economic assistance and transfer of technology.²⁸ This leads us to the importance of the declaration to international economic law.

IMPORTANCE OF STOCKHOLM DECLARATION TO INTERNATIONAL ECONOMIC LAW

In an attempt at discussing the theoretical basis of environmental law, it is safe to note that it is achievable by an analysis of the principles on which it is founded. However, giving the plethora of principles that form the foundation of most environmental law and in this case, the Stockholm declaration in 1972, it becomes horrendous to discuss all principles. This constraint, therefore limit this paper to principles that have strong bearing and relation to international economic law. Consequently, specific attention will be paid to two of such fundamental principles of the Stockholm declaration: the principle of sustainable development and the intergenerational equity.

²⁷ See M. FitMaurice, The Principle of Sustainable Development in International Development Law. International Sustainable Development Law. Vol, I. Pg 6 (UNESCO- EOLSS Sample Chapter) (To access all the 25 pages of the Chapter, visit <http://www.eolss.net/Eolss-sampleAllChapters.aspx>).

²⁸ Ibid. at pg 6

Sustainable development

As already noted, the United Nations Conference on the Human Environment (UNCHE) was held in Stockholm in 1972, and it became the start point for the development of environmental law on the international plane.²⁹ The development of environmental law took another turn in 1987 with the making public, Report of the World Commission on Environment and Development. The Report, titled 'Our Common Future' emphasised the need for a global co-operation geared towards the formulation of common survival modalities by all of humanity and to reduce the exhaustion of the resources as well as pollution of the environment.³⁰ The Conference also stressed the relationship between the environment and the concept of sustainable development.

Sustainability is an admixture of policies for environmental protection, economic development,³¹ and poverty eradication.³² Its scope includes the integration of countries and regions as it recognises that the environment is as interconnected as the human body. An 'unsustainable situation' occurs when natural capital (the sum total of nature's resources) is used up faster than it can be replenished. That human activity should use nature's resources at a rate at which they can be replenished naturally is the linchpin of the concept of sustainability. Consequently, sustainability is intertwined with the concept of carrying capacity: when man's exploitation of the environment exceeds her carrying capacity and results in environmental degradation, the corollary is the inability of the earth to sustain life and further down the road, extinction of life on earth. Sustainable development has been

²⁹ See Report of the United Nations Conference on the Human Environment. Op.cit at n 2.

³⁰ See P. Malanczuk: Akehurst's Modern Introduction to International Law (7th ed.) (London: Routledge, 1997) page 241

³¹ J. Thornton & S. Beckwith: Environmental Law (2nd ed.) (London: Sweet & Maxwell, 2004) page 46.

³² Ibid. The Brundtland Report found that there exists a nexus between poverty and environmental problems.

given a place of honour as it has become the leading concept in environmental policies globally and finds support in an eclectic collection of thoughts.³³

Its principles have found their way into not a few international environmental treaties³⁴ and municipal legislation.³⁵ In the *Gabcikovo –Nagymaros project* case, the International Court of Justice commented on the concept of sustainable development as follows:

“Throughout the ages, mankind has, for economic and other reasons, constantly interfered with nature. In the past, this was often done without consideration of the effect upon the environment. Owing to new scientific insights and to a growing awareness of the risks for mankind... for present and future generations... of the pursuit of such interventions at an unconsidered and unabated pace, new norms and standards have been developed, set forth in a great number of instruments during the last two decades. Such new norms have to be taken into consideration, and such new standards given proper weight, not only when States contemplate new activities but also when continuing with activities begun in the past. This need to reconcile economic development with protection of the

³³ The sacred texts, beliefs and teachings of the world’s religions are also supportive of sustainable development. Buddha taught respect for all life. Native American religious beliefs recognise the connectedness of all life. The Jewish and Christian traditions teach that God made the world, that God declared creation to be good, that the earth belongs to God, and that humans are to exercise stewardship or dominion (not domination) over creation. See J. C. Dernbach: ‘Why Lawyers Should Care about Sustainable Development’, *Ibid* at pg 37; W. Ajai: ‘Achieving Environmental Protection Through the Vehicle of Human Rights: Some Conceptual, Legal and Third World Problems’ (1995) Vol. 2 No. 1 UBLJ 41, 44.

³⁴ See for example the Convention on Environmental Impact Assessment in Transboundary Context (1991) 30 ILM 802; Article 2, Kyoto Protocol to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, FCCC/CP/1997/7/Add. 1, reprinted in 1998 ILM 22; No. 9 of the Preamble to the EC Directive concerning Integrated Pollution Prevention and Control (IPPC) 1996 Council Directive 96/61/EC of 24 September 1996, Official Journal L 257/26

³⁵ See for example Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) Act; the US National Environmental Policy Act of 1969; Article 4 of the Japanese Basic Environmental Law, 1993, Law No. 91 of 1993.

environment is aptly expressed in the concept of sustainable development."³⁶

As earlier stated, sustainable development is an admixture: it encompasses other principles which analysis of will bring about a better understanding of the ramification of sustainability. However, this study is not exhaustive; but in this case, specific mention will be paid to some concepts, among others that may contribute towards sustainable development. These are: Policy Integration, Sustainable Resource Use, Equity, Transparency and Public Participation, and finally Biodiversity.³⁷

In the interest of policy integration, references to sustainable development as an overarching policy goal are being included in trade agreements. For example, the preamble to the North American Free Trade Agreement (NAFTA) states that one of its primary purposes is to:

*"Contribute to the harmonious development and expansion of world trade...in a manner consistent with environmental protection and conservation;... promote sustainable development;...[and] strengthen the development and enforcement of environmental laws and regulations."*³⁸

Similarly, the Uruguay Round Agreement establishing the World Trade Organisation (WTO) includes references to the objective of sustainable development and to the need to protect and preserve the environment:

"Recognising that their relations in the field of trade and economic endeavour should be conducted with a view to

³⁶ Gabcikovo – Nagaymaros Project (Hungary v. Slovakia), 37 ILM 162 (1998) (Sept. 25, 1997) Para.140.

³⁷ See Environmental Principles and concepts; Organisation for Economic co-operation and development. Paris 1995. Available at <http://www.oecd.org/trade/environmentalandtrade/39918312.pdf>. Accessed on 18th December, 2015.

³⁸ Ibid.

*raising standards of living; ...while allowing for the optimal use of the world's resources in accordance with the objective of sustainable development, seeking both to protect and preserve the environment and enhance the means for doing so in a manner consistent with their respective needs and concerns at different levels of economic development."*³⁹

It should also be noted that the Treaty establishing the European Community (EC Treaty),⁴⁰ provides in its article 2:

"The Community shall have as its task... to promote throughout the Community... sustainable and non-inflationary growth respecting the environment,..."

Financial Institutions and Sustainable development in the developing countries.

It is important to stress that Stockholm declaration of 1972 and of course other international environmental treaties and agreement, set the pace for certain pattern international financial institutions assumes in the discharge of their respective activities and services rendered. As earlier noted, the Stockholm declaration is an essential instrument that seeks to regulate humankind activities in relation to his environment and the need for an interface between economic development and the environment with emphasis on developing countries. Therefore, the declarations bring about the need for developed countries to coordinate their international financial activities in a way that addressed and assist developing nations in areas

³⁹ Ibid.

⁴⁰ Ibid. Treaty establishing the European Community, as amended by the Treaty on European Union, Maastricht, 7 February 1992.

of economic development and environmental issues. This leads us to examine in brief the role of International Financial Institution in sustainable development.

One of the subsidiaries of the World Bank group⁴¹ (W.B.G) is the international finance corporation (I.F.C) – a private arm of the group. Most activities of the W.B.G, albeit the International Financial Corporation (I.F.C) focused on developing countries⁴² in field such as (a) environmental protection – i.e. pollution reduction, established and enforcing regulations (b) Agriculture and rural development – i.e. irrigation and rural services. (c) Infrastructure - i.e. roads urban regeneration and electricity. (d) Human development i.e.- education and health (e) governance (f) investment in the private sectors (g) providing insurance etc.⁴³ The activities of International Financial Corporation (I.F.C) are sum up in three categories, which are;

- (a) Investment Services
- (b) Advisory Services.
- (c) Asset management company.⁴⁴

Aside the investment services, of concerned from the above activities of International Financial Corporation (I.F.C) are the Advisory services. Advisory services were provided in terms of support to corporate decision making regarding business, environment, social impact and sustainability. Advices on infrastructure development and public- private partnership were offered to government, in a bid to encourage reforms that improve the trade friendliness

⁴¹ The World Bank Group consists of (1) the International Bank for Reconstruction and Development and (2) the International Development Association, which lend to governments (these two institutions are known collectively as the World Bank); (3) the International Finance Corporation (IFC), which lends to private companies; (4) the Multilateral Investment Guarantee Agency; and (5) the International Center for Settlement of Investment Disputes. This paper focuses on the World Bank and the IFC.

⁴² As at January 2011, I.F.C has supported almost \$22 billion of trade transactions of the finance program and liquidity program. Over one third of the trade supported was in Latin America, 22 percent in sub Sahara-Africa and 16 percent in middle East and north America. See the I.F.C approach to international trade finance, available at <http://www.brettonwoodsproject.org/art-568568>. Accessed on 15th December, 2015.

⁴³ Available at http://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/world_Bank_group. Accessed on 15th December, 2012.

⁴⁴ Available: http://www1.ifc.org/wps/wcm/connect/CORP_EXT_Content/IFC_EXTERNAL_CORPORATE_Site/what+we+do/ accessed on 15th December 2015.

that foster a suitable investment climate. The International Financial Corporation (I.F.C) attempts to guide business towards more sustainable practices, particularly with regards to having good governance, supporting women in business and proactively combating climate change.⁴⁵ Suffice to state that over half of the World Bank funding is now channelled through “development policy loans”⁴⁶

Intergenerational equity

The principle of intergenerational equity precipitates the conclusion that environmental resources and assets - such as the quality and diversity of environment - do not 'belong' to any generation but are to be administered and preserved in trust for all future generations.⁴⁷ On the surface, it resembles the principle of sustainable development. The difference between the two principles is that intergenerational equity is founded on the principle of distributive justice,⁴⁸ a principle rooted in egalitarianism, equality, equity and utilitarianism; while the principle of sustainable development brings to the fore the issues of needs and limitations, which in turn give birth to a situation different from that where egalitarianism, equality and equity hold sway⁴⁹

The thinking that humanity – past, present and future generations – have an equal right to the wealth of the environment has influenced the drafting of legislation. For example, the preamble to the *Legality of the Threat or Use of Nuclear Weapons (Advisory Opinion of July*

⁴⁵ See international finance corporation (2010): where innovation meets impact (report). World Bank Group. Available at http://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/international_finance_corporate#section7. Accessed on 16th December, 2015.

⁴⁶ See Vince McElhinny, World Bank and DPLS: What Middle Income Countries Wants, 4th Febuary,2011. Available at <http://www.bicusa.org/en/Article.12351.aspx>.

⁴⁷ See business dictionary. Available at <http://www.businessdictionary.com/definition/intergenerational-equity.html>.

⁴⁸ Distributive justice is a normative principle which posits that the benefits and burdens of the wealth of a community should be shared on the basis of equality. The principle underscores the fact that everyone should have the same level of goods and services. In relation to the environment, it portends that it is only fair that every generation is exposed to the same quality of wealth/ resources of the environment notwithstanding its place in the continuum of time.

⁴⁹ See business dictionary. Op. Cit at n 47.

8, 1996)⁵⁰ states that the environment ‘represents the living space, the quality of life and the very health of human beings, including generations unborn’. Also, the *Charter of Economic Rights and Duties of States*⁵¹ asserts that ‘the protection, preservation and enhancement of the environment for the present and future generations are the responsibility of all States’. Principle 1 of the *Stockholm Declaration* states that man bears a solemn responsibility to protect and improve the environment for present and future generations. The *Rio Declaration* formulates the principle more broadly:

*“The right to development must be fulfilled so as to equitably meet developmental and environmental needs of present and future generations.”*⁵²

Intergenerational equity is based on a moral obligation which is rooted in the traditional conception of equity and every generation owe this to each other thus making them beneficiaries and trustees *inter se*. It is the duty of the present generation to future generations to pass on the natural and cultural resources of the planet in no worse condition than received and to provide reasonable access to the legacy for the present generation.⁵³ There is definitely no equality and equity in their utilisation of the wealth of the environment as these concepts propel them differently.

Subsumed in this principle is the ‘no – harm’ or ‘due diligence’ rule. The rule which has coloured environmental policies, legislation - both municipal⁵⁴ and international⁵⁵ has its

⁵⁰ 1996 ICJ 95, 35 ILM 809, 821.

⁵¹ UN GAOR, 29th Sess., Supp. No. 31, at 50, 55, UN Doc. A/9631 (1975); reprinted in 14 ILM 251, 260, (1975).

⁵² Principle 3, *Ibid*

⁵³ See A. D’Amato: ‘Do We Owe a Duty to Future Generations to Preserve the Global Environment?’, (1990) 84 Am. J. Int’l L, 190, 198; EB Weiss: ‘Our Rights and Obligations to Future Generations for the Environment’, (1990) 84 Am. J. Int’l L, 198 where the writer analysed the justifications for, and implications of, intergenerational equity.

⁵⁴ See generally Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) Act.

⁵⁵ UN Convention on the Law of the Sea, 21 ILM 1261 (1982); the Preamble of the 1985 Vienna Convention for the Protection of the Ozone Layer, 26 ILM 1529 (1988); UN Framework Convention on Climate Change Convention, 31 ILM 849

foundations in the *Trail Smelter Arbitration* and the ICJ decision in the *Corfu Channel*⁵⁶ case. They both set the tune as it regards transfrontier/ transboundary environmental pollution. The principle espoused by these authorities is to the effect that no state has the right to use its territory in a manner that is capable of causing injury to the territory of another. The *Stockholm Declaration* further expatiated on the principle. It provides that:

*“States have, in accordance with the Charter of the United Nations and the principles of international law, the sovereign right to exploit their own resources pursuant to their own environmental (and developmental) policies and the responsibility to ensure that activities within their jurisdiction or control do not cause damage to the environment of other States or of areas beyond national jurisdiction.”*⁵⁷

It must be stated that while intergenerational equity concerns are as old as mankind – the 2008/09 World Financial Crisis, an aging Western world population and climate change have put a new stance on irreversible destruction of future potential. Next generations’ debt, unfeasible social welfare and sustainability threats and intergenerational equity have to be continuously addressed as an urgent topic of concern. Understanding intergenerational equity appears to hold opportunities to implement financial social responsibility, social welfare reforms and ecologic sustainability in the aftermath of the 2008/09 World Financial Crisis.⁵⁸ Hence, international financial institutions through the machinery of financial implementation,

⁵⁶ ICJ Reports (1949) 22.

⁵⁷ See Principle 21.

⁵⁸ See Julia M. Ptaschunder: On the Social Representations of Intergenerational Equity. Electronic copy available at: <http://ssrn.com/abstract=2011359>

scrutinize the need for funds provided for both the developed and developing countries to meet the intergenerational equity principles.⁵⁹

One issue that ought not to escape mention is the issue of climate change. Obviously one of the relative shortcomings of the Stockholm declaration of 1972 is that the declaration did not explicitly incorporate in its principle this ongoing phenomenon in the UN International environmental conference.⁶⁰ However, flat condemnation of the declaration in this regard holds less weight. The Rio declaration of 1992- the brain child of the Stockholm declaration addresses the issues of climate change. Recently, International Financial Institutions' (IFIs), especially the World Bank, have had a significant presence at the UN climate change negotiations.⁶¹ In fact, since 2008,⁶² the World Bank has managed the \$6.3 billion "climate investment funds," which have helped to finance climate related projects while governments negotiated a more permanent financing mechanism. In December 2010,⁶³ government signed the Cancun Agreement and created a Green Climate Fund as the central mechanism for financing the global response to climate change.⁶⁴ More so, the World Bank was appointed as an interim trustee of the fund. In the coming years, the Bank will continue to play a leading role in directing finance to climate change efforts, and in setting the precedents for future

⁵⁹ See the I.F.C approach to international trade finance, available at <http://www.brettonwoodsproject.org/art-568568>. Accessed on 15th December, 2012. See also Greening the international financial institutions (IFIs): Finance for the next decades' Development. Kirk Herbertson, World Resources Institute for Stakeholder forum (2012). Available at [http://www.stakeholderforum.org/fileadmin/files/greening the IFIs. pdf](http://www.stakeholderforum.org/fileadmin/files/greening_the_IFIs.pdf). Accessed on 18th December, 2015.

⁶⁰ There was a meeting of the world leaders on the issue of climate change in November 2013, in Doha, United Arab Emirates.

⁶¹ From the early 1980s, concerns on Climate Change were more progressively institutionalized in transnational organizations, conventions, conferences, protocols and recently agreement; such as Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), Kyoto Protocol, Rio Conference on Environmental and Development, Paris Agreement among others.

⁶² <http://climatechange.worldbank.org/content/climate-finance-and-world-bank-facts>. Accessed on 19th December, 2015.

⁶³ See Greening the international financial institutions (IFIs): Finance for the next decades' Development. Kirk Herbertson, World Resources Institute for Stakeholder forum (2012). Available at [http://www.stakeholderforum.org/fileadmin/files/greening the IFIs. pdf](http://www.stakeholderforum.org/fileadmin/files/greening_the_IFIs.pdf). Accessed on 18th December, 2015.

⁶⁴ Ibid.

financing. The Bank's performance will be crucial to the success of the UN climate change agreement.

CONCLUSION

Undoubtedly, Stockholm declaration of 1972 had exercised profound influence on humankind activities in relation to his environment. Safe to submit that Stockholm Declaration was perhaps the first major international environmental law instrument that introduced the idea of conserving natural resources onto the agenda of international economic law. Principle 2, 3 and 5 of the declaration speak of the need to conserve natural resources. Until this point, international economic law had sought to define and strengthen the rights of sovereign states to exploit their natural resources (whether renewable or non- renewable) through various instruments, such as the concept of permanent sovereignty over natural resource. However, while endorsing the right of states, principle 21 of the declaration sought to reconcile it with the need for environmental protection.

The desire to protect the environment had triggered both social and political tinkering in international financial institution. The principles of sustainable development, inter generational equity and other related concepts garnered from the historical landmark Stockholm declaration, and of course subsequent environmental instrument in like terms, had change the ways and manners, international financial institutions carry out businesses. In many cases, their approach is now more focus on environmental and economic development in the developing countries. International Financial Institutions (I.F.I) are now geared towards making investment in a wider variety of ways. The World Bank and other I.F.I invested directly in projects- such that affects the environment. Safeguard policies and other bank approaches to sustainable development were designed with the type of this investment in mind. All thanks to Stockholm declaration of 1972.